

A systematic review of urban ecosystem disservices and its evaluation: Key findings and implications

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ABSTRACT

Ecosystem functions generate both ecosystem services (ES) and ecosystem disservices (EDS). EDS are aspects of ecosystems that have a negative impact on human well-being. Despite growing recognition of EDS, comprehensive reviews exploring their nature across different geographical contexts and the evaluation methods utilized to study them remains scarce. This study addresses this gap through a systematic review and bibliometric analysis. A search in the Web of Science (WoS) database identified 1098 articles, from which 49 papers were selected using the ROSES flow diagram, including one pre-screened article from Google Scholar. The bibliometric analysis in VOSviewer revealed four clusters, highlighting key themes and hotspots in EDS research. The reviewed papers primarily used case study methodologies, focusing on European cities, with limited research from the global South, where socio-cultural and environmental differences may reveal different EDS dynamics. Our review identified 24 EDS types and various evaluation methods, including qualitative analysis, remote sensing and GIS, sampling method and mixed-methods which reveals a predominance of qualitative assessments of EDS, with limited quantitative approaches. Moreover, the impact of EDS on vulnerable groups are rarely explored, indicating a gap in urban environment research. This review calls for the development of evidence-based quantitative methods to assess EDS and urges their integration within ES frameworks for a more holistic understanding of urban ecosystem complexities. By bridging gaps in geographical coverage, addressing socio-cultural dimensions, and focusing on the needs of vulnerable populations, future research can guide urban planners towards more sustainable, equitable, and resilient cities.

1. Introduction

Urbanization is rapidly reshaping global landscapes, with over half of the world's population currently living in cities, a figure projected to reach 90% by the end of the 21st century (Artmann et al., 2017; Hosaka et al., 2017). As cities grow, ensuring quality of life in urban areas has become a pressing concern, driving policies and strategic development plans aimed at sustainable and resilient urban environments. One critical aspect of this is the role of urban ecosystems, which provide a range of benefits to urban residents in the form of ecosystem services (ES). These services promote quality of life by contributing to environmental health and enhancing human well-being (Hosaka et al., 2017; Larson et al., 2019; von Döhren and Haase, 2022). However, it is also increasingly acknowledged that people's interactions with nature are not always positive, and the same ecosystem function can also generate negative impacts on human well-being, known as ecosystem disservices (Azmy et al., 2016; Gutierrez-Arellano and Mulligan, 2018; Hosaka

et al., 2017; von Döhren and Haase, 2022; Wood et al., 2022).

Ecosystem disservices (hereinafter referred to as EDS) are ecosystem functions or processes that are perceived as harmful, unpleasant or economically detrimental to human well-being (Ala-Hulkko et al., 2019; Azmy et al., 2016; Lyytimäki, 2014; Vaz et al., 2017). In urban settings, these disservices can include infrastructure damage from tree roots and tree felling, health risks from poorly managed natural areas, the threat of animal attacks, and the fear of crime in neglected green spaces (Pineda-Guerrero et al., 2021; Vaz et al., 2017; Von Döhren and Haase, 2015). While ES are well recognized for their positive contributions to urban life, EDS highlight the complexity of human-nature interactions, particularly in urban residential areas, where high population density and intense human-nature interactions lead to more noticeable impacts on human health, economics, and urban planning (Kathryn Rodgman et al., 2024). The importance of addressing EDS in urban planning strategies along with ES to improve the wellbeing of urban residents is therefore called upon also in the context of inclusive planning (Skryhan

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and Shkaruba, 2022).

The concept of EDS emerged in literature as a response to early attempts to characterize ES as mostly beneficial ecosystem processes (Saunders, 2020a; Vaz et al., 2017). Since the first study on EDS published in 2006 (Wu et al., 2021), the topic has been the subject of numerous opinion papers (Blanco et al., 2019; Lyytimäki, 2015). Lyytimäki & Sipilä (2009) were the first to conceptualize and explain the term, and it has gained traction in scientific literature as an important aspect of urban ecosystem research (Ala-Hulkko et al., 2019). The most unified and accepted definition, provided by Shackleton et al. (2016), describes EDS as “the ecosystem generated functions, processes and attributes that result in perceived or actual negative impacts on human wellbeing” (Campagne et al., 2018; Larson et al., 2019; Vaz et al., 2017). Like ES, EDS are influenced by both ecological and human elements within socio-ecological systems (SES) (Blanco et al., 2019), making them highly context-specific and variable across different cultural and geographical contexts (Skryhan and Shkaruba, 2022). For example, while an urban forest might provide shade and recreational benefits in one context, it may be seen as a source of fear, litter, or maintenance costs in another. This dual nature of ecosystem functions, where the same process can be seen as both a service and a disservice, highlights the complexity of human-nature interactions in urban areas (Azmy et al., 2016; Hosaka et al., 2017; von Döhren and Haase, 2022).

Despite the growing body of research on EDS, the topic remains a subject of ongoing and contentious debate, as they consider negative perceptions of nature. However, disregarding EDS is not viable. With urban populations rising, there is an escalating demand for inclusive planning integrating new and existing green spaces, exploring innovative green and blue infrastructure, and adapting them to the current urbanization context (Stoia et al., 2022; Shkaruba et al., 2021). In this regard, it is important to incorporate EDS into both research and policy discussions about ES and their management. This is because EDS negatively impact human well-being and failing to address them in management plans would compromise the beneficial relationship between ES, biodiversity, and human well-being (Shackleton et al., 2016), potentially leading to inadequate management strategies and policies that fail to address the full spectrum of ecological complexities around us. Understanding the ES-EDS dichotomy in urban settings is therefore crucial for fostering the development of resilient and sustainable cities (Potgieter et al., 2019a).

Establishing a shared understanding on what constitutes an ecosystem disservice, distinguishing it from what it is not, and comprehending how these disservices evolve within diverse cultural, planning, and ecological contexts is crucial, and is pivotal to managing the intricate relationships between ecosystems and human well-being within socio-ecological systems (Saunders, 2020b). Hence, this study aims to **provide a better understanding and address the nature of EDS in existing literature by identifying key themes and synthesizing various evaluation and mapping frameworks used to analyze EDS**. This study will help us to gain better knowledge and suggest its implementation into urban planning particularly given the rising urbanisation. Building on the conceptual framework given by Potschin-Young et al. (2018); Wu et al. (2021), the EDS cascade given in Fig. 1 explains how evidence-based research on urban EDS and its impact derived from ecosystem function and processes can aid its integration into urban planning and policies.

The following research questions were addressed in this paper.

- RQ 1: What are the thematic and geographical foci of ecosystem disservices research, and what are the determinants?
- RQ 2: What is the state of mapping/evaluation/qualitative and quantitative methodology applied for the analysis of EDS?
- RQ 3: What are the limitations of existing EDS frameworks, and what can potentially be explored to address urban planning and management challenges?

Although research on EDS has grown significantly; to the best of our knowledge, no systematic review has been conducted to consolidate the diverse range of themes, approaches and methodologies associated with the study of EDS despite its significant implications for managing ecosystems more holistically. To fill this gap and address the above questions, we adopted a systematic review methodology and we adhered to the guidelines set by Collaboration for Environmental Evidence (2018) to examine the existing scientific literature, focusing on the key themes, types of EDS addressed, methods and applications related to EDS, and try to clarify the terminology and move the field of EDS toward a more consistent and widely accepted framework and scientific practice. Additionally, this review offers insights into potential research directions, providing a roadmap for operationalizing the EDS concept in ways that enhance its scientific rigor and practical relevance.

Fig. 1. Ecosystem Disservices (EDS) cascade model adapted from Potschin-Young et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2021.

The review paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the methodology used: data collection, extraction and analysis, while section 3 presents the main findings according to the research questions. Finally, section 4 discusses the findings and implications of the study and section 5 draws key conclusions from this work.

2. Materials and methods

This study employed a systematic literature review (SLR) of publications and a bibliometric analysis for visualization. The systematic review is based on the RepORting standards for Systematic Evidence

Fig. 2. ROSES flow diagram for systematic reviews indicative of the searching, screening, and critical appraisal of articles. (n: number of articles) (Haddaway NR, Macura B, Whaley P, and Pullin AS. 2017. ROSES flow diagram for systematic reviews. Version 1.0 <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.5897389>).

Syntheses (ROSES) to offer an overview of peer-reviewed journal articles on EDS (Fig. 2). ROSES, tailored specifically for systematic reviews in the field of environmental research, offers a standardized framework to ensure methodological rigor and transparency (Haddaway et al., 2018). The study follows a structured process that identifies the data sources for the search, the search keywords, and the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Additionally, bibliometric analysis, a quantitative method for mapping research trends and themes, was used to visualize and analyze an overview of the distribution and connections within the research field (Cancino and Merigo, 2015).

2.1. Data collection

Most of the data has been collected from the Web of Science (WoS) database. Its Core Collection covers a wide range of rigorously peer-reviewed records and disciplines that maximize representativeness and accessibility of literature (Martín-Martín et al., 2021). The scope of the analysis included several parameters: publication type, geographical scope, population, outcomes, study design and methods, and language of publication.

First, a set of search terms was compiled according to the study’s objective and research questions. Literature searches were then performed using a combination of the following search terms: ‘Ecosystem disservices’, ‘Ecosystem disservices’ AND ‘urban’, ‘Ecosystem disservices’ AND ‘evaluation’, ‘Ecosystem disservices’ AND ‘mapping’, ‘Ecosystem disservices’ AND ‘challenges’, ‘Ecosystem disservices’ AND ‘gaps’. The database search was conducted in March 2024 (Table 1). Review articles, meta-data, gray literature and book indices were excluded from the pool as these sources did not provide novel researches but were summaries of the other included articles. A total of 1098 research articles therefore retained for potential inclusion.

2.2. Data extraction and analysis

The process of identifying relevant publications for review involves the screening of selected records. Out of the total 1098 publications, 464 duplicates were identified and removed. 634 unique publications were further examined based on titles and abstracts in terms of their relevance. After reviewing the titles and abstracts, 257 articles were selected for full-text assessment. 34 of those articles were not available online and were therefore excluded. Upon reading the full text of the remaining 223 articles, 162 were eliminated based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria set in Table 2. Studies not fulfilling the inclusion criteria were excluded. One further pre-screened paper from Google Scholar was also

Table 1
The searching terms used and the total number of articles from each database.

Database	Searching string	Searching terms	No. of articles	Date of acquisition
Web of Science	main searching terms – using title, abstract, keywords and source	‘Ecosystem disservices’	615	18-03-2024
		‘Ecosystem disservices’ AND ‘urban’	256	18-03-2024
		‘Ecosystem disservices’ AND ‘evaluation’	23	18-03-2024
		‘Ecosystem disservices’ AND ‘mapping’	56	19-03-2023
		‘Ecosystem disservices’ AND ‘challenges’	108	21-03-2024
		‘Ecosystem disservices’ AND ‘gaps’	40	21-03-2024
		Total	1098	

Table 2
Inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Variable	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion criteria
Intervention	EDS related intervention aimed at evaluating the negative impact of ecosystem functions on humans.	Studies not directly related to evaluation of EDS or those primarily focused on ES without considering EDS.
Publication type	Peer-reviewed articles, or book chapters.	Reviews papers, gray literature, meta-data or book indices.
Geographical scope	Studies conducted in urban and peri-urban areas.	Studies conducted in farmlands, agricultural lands, or rural areas.
Population	Human populations affected by EDS. Populations residing in and around urban green and blue spaces (UGBS).	Populations living in non-urban areas.
Outcome	Studies reporting measurable outcomes related to EDS, such as health impacts, economic losses, or impediments to people’s daily lives.	Studies lacking clear outcome measures.
Study design	Studies utilizing a range of methodologies, including mapping, qualitative and quantitative approaches	Studies lacking sufficient detail or methodologies or data sources. Studies with inadequate study designs (e.g., case reports, or opinion pieces).
Language	Articles written in English.	Articles in different languages other than English.

included for critical appraisal based on its relevance to the research questions using the same eligibility criteria.

Of the remaining 62 articles, 13 were either generalized studies or duplicates of other studies, and were therefore excluded to ensure that only unique studies we represented. Publications written on other languages than English were excluded either. As a result, 49 unique articles have been retained for the final review.

2.3. Bibliometric analysis

To complement the systematic review, bibliometric analysis was performed on the 49 selected articles. The analysis was conducted using VOSviewer, a software tool developed by van Eck and Waltman (2010). VOSviewer operates in a Java environment and can import pieces of literature in WoS formats. It implements a visualization of network mapping technique, with nodes representing keywords, and lines connecting nodes indicate the relationships between them based on co-authorship, co-occurrence of keywords, and co-citation patterns.

3. Findings

3.1. General characteristics of reviewed articles

3.1.1. Publication years and journals

The earliest paper among the 49 selected was published in 2013 and the number of publications has increased significantly in the past ten years (Fig. 3). Since the search has been done in early March 2024, only one paper from the pool has appeared in 2024, and the downward trend in 2024 does not reflect an actual situation.

The highest number of eligible EDS-related papers have been published in a journal directly addressing the issues of green and blue in cities (‘Urban Forestry and Urban Greening’, 10 articles). Other significant contributions came from journals with broader scopes in land-use, environmental management, and sustainability. These include ‘Ecosystem Services’ (4 articles), ‘Land Use Policy’ (3 articles), ‘Land’, ‘Forests’, ‘Urban Science’ ‘Sustainability’, ‘Ecosystems and people’, and ‘Journal of Environmental Management’, with 2 articles each (Fig. 4). The

Fig. 3. Number of publications selected for final review (N = 49).

Fig. 4. Journals with the highest number of publications of selected articles.

remaining 20 articles were distributed across various other journals, reflecting the wide-ranging interest and multidisciplinary nature of EDS research.

3.1.2. Thematic trends: keywords analysis

The key themes of EDS-related papers and larger contexts in which they were published have been revealed through the analysis of keywords. A network map based on the information extracted from 49 selected papers visualizes the most co-occurred words by clustering 2 or more occurrences using VOSviewer for keyword co-occurrence analysis to illustrate the distribution characteristics of research hotspots and themes in EDS. Four meaningful clusters were therefore formed (Fig. 5).

In Fig. 5, each node represents a keyword, and the size of the nodes corresponds to the number of instances it was mentioned. The biggest co-occurrence nodes are associated with keywords such as *ecosystem disservices*, *benefits*, *urban planning*, *green infrastructure*, *management* and *human health*. These keywords indicate a focus on managing urban green infrastructure to maximize human health benefits while minimizing EDS, integral to urban planning strategies. The connecting lines between nodes reflect keyword-co-occurrence, forming distinctive clusters (marked by different colors on Fig. 5).

Cluster 1 (yellow) consists of keywords such as: *behavior*, *cultural ecosystem services*, *disservices*, *infrastructure*, *landscape*, *management*, and *social values*, the most frequent being *management*, *infrastructure* and *disservices*. The papers from this area focus on the management of infrastructure based on social values, influencing both cultural ES and EDS.

Cluster 2 (green) includes the following set of keywords: *forests*, *urban forest*, *perception*, *green infrastructure*, *risk*, *time*, *attitude*, *environment* and *health*. This cluster explores how forests, as key components of green infrastructure, shape public perceptions and attitudes over time, influencing the management of environmental risks and human health.

Cluster 3 (red) is dominated by such keywords as ‘*urban planning*’ and ‘*human health*’ with less frequent keywords being *urban green infrastructure*, *parks*, *perspective*, *urban*, *sustainability*, *air pollution*, *GIS* and *physical activity*. This cluster brings together papers dealing with urban planning strategies to create more sustainable urban green infrastructure such as parks that support human health and wellbeing while reducing disservices such as air pollution. Most of these articles are based on GIS (Geographic Information System) analysis.

Cluster 4 (blue) is formed around such keywords as ‘*ecosystem disservices*’ and ‘*benefits*’. Other keywords are: *strategies*, *green space*,

Fig. 5. Co-occurrence network map of keywords derived from studies selected for review.

conservation, classification, tree, green space, vegetation, community, children, pollen, invasive species, and tradeoffs. Articles in this cluster focus on evaluating the trade-offs between EDS and benefits, developing conservation strategies for green spaces, classifying vegetation, and understanding the impacts on communities by pollen and invasive species, and health implications.

3.1.3. Geographical distribution of EDS case studies

The distribution of case studies on EDS, based on the reviewed articles, demonstrates a diverse geographic scope with a significant emphasis on Europe as shown in Figs. 6 and 7 (a). The majority of studies (20 articles) included case studies across 11 European countries: Belarus, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, and the United Kingdom. In Asia, 14 articles featured case studies from cities in 8 countries: China, India, Japan, Philippines, Singapore, Taiwan, Turkey and Vietnam, 6 articles in Africa (2 countries; Namibia and South Africa), 4 in Southern America (Brazil and Colombia), 2 articles in Australia, 1 in Northern America (USA) and 2 articles featured case studies across multiple continents: one of these covered Europe (Germany, Sweden and Russia), Australia and Oceania (Australia and New Zealand) and North America (USA) while the other included case studies from Europe (Sweden) and North America (USA). The country with most case studies are Italy and South Africa with 5 articles (Fig. 7b). The cities with their basic characteristics are listed in Table 3.

The ecosystem types studied and referenced in the reviewed papers for case studies comprises of UGS in general, urban residential areas, urban landscape, parks, forests, lawns, blue-green spaces and also blue spaces like urban wetlands and lakes (Fig. 6).

3.2. Ecosystem disservices types

The different EDS studied in these literatures were grouped based on their types as shown in Table 4. Each article addressed one to four EDS types. To highlight the types of EDS analyzed in the selected papers, they were grouped under 4 main EDS groups and 7 categories, loosely building on the classification suggested by Skryhan and Shkaruba (2022), consisting a total of 24 different EDS types spread across geographically (Table 5).

Most of the articles analyzed two or more EDS. The EDS most commonly mentioned is allergies and diseases associated with urban green spaces (Fig. 8)

3.3. Different evaluation methods of EDS

The reviewed papers used the following evaluation methods and/or techniques (Fig. 9): Qualitative analysis (19 articles), Remote sensing and GIS (11 articles), Sampling methods – field sampling and laboratory sampling methods (3 articles) and Mixed-methods approaches (16 articles) comprising of a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods (Table 6).

3.3.1. Qualitative analysis (questionnaire/interview/literature mining)

Qualitative sociological analysis has been the most frequently used method to study ecosystem EDS in urban settings (19 out of the 49 reviewed articles). The most commonly used analytical strategy were integrated frameworks featuring interviews, discussions, literature mining or questionnaires as shown in Table 6.

These methods were used to study such EDS as conflicts arising from human-wildlife interactions (Eriksson et al., 2020; Hosaka et al., 2017;

Fig. 6. Geographical distribution of EDS case studies by country, highlighting the various ecosystem types referenced in each case.

König et al., 2021; Luetkemeier et al., 2023), invasive plants (Potgieter et al., 2019b; Sheergojri et al., 2022; Vaz et al., 2017; Yam et al., 2015), tree failure and tree-related nuisances (Roman et al., 2021), harmful algal bloom (Willis et al., 2018), tick-bite risk (Oosterbroek et al., 2024), dust pollution created from lawns (Ignatieva et al., 2020), deteriorating water quality (Wood et al., 2022), snake-bite risk (Hwang and Roscoe, 2017), unmanaged and unpleasant sites (Skryhan and Shkaruba, 2022), allergenic potential (Artmann et al., 2017), infrastructure damage (Belaire et al., 2015), the presence of insects/pests and pavement or car staining caused by tree fruits (Stoia et al., 2022). In addition, Shah et al. (2023) used literature mining to collect data from research reports, government reports and scientific literature using an energy based assessment to evaluate the potential of constructed wetlands related to human health, expenses and disservices, while adopting a framework to study the ESs related to urban constructed framework.

Most of these studies used qualitative analysis to understand residents' preferences regarding urban nature. Integrating stakeholder knowledge is essential for project success and the generation of useable knowledge to enable long-term reforms (Caggiu et al., 2023; Luetkemeier et al., 2023). Qualitative analysis captures humans' perspective experience with nature around them, providing insights into the numerous impacts on human well-being and identifies critical factors - such as geographical, cultural, and socioeconomic variables - that influence nature and severity of disservices in various urban settings (Sheergojri et al., 2022; Stoia et al., 2022; Willis et al., 2018). This approach, therefore, helps to inform policy, planning and management strategies by incorporating local knowledge and residents' perspective in ensuring policies, in particular to consider the most exposed groups.

3.3.2. Remote sensing and GIS

11 articles were based on remote sensing and GIS analysis. Such methods were used to identify areas affected by invasive plants (IAPs) (Potgieter et al., 2019a), trees causing allergies and diseases (Juanita et al., 2019; Manfra et al., 2022; Prigioniero et al., 2022; von Döhren and

Haase, 2022), neglected, degraded and unpleasant sites and the impact of street trees on urban infrastructure (Jombo et al., 2020; Baumeister et al., 2022) employed a map-based online questionnaire tool (Public Participatory Geographical Information System, GIS) to assess the perceptions of ES and EDS in urban forests. Oosterbroek et al., 2023 utilized a GIS-based spatial model to model greenspace benefits and burdens for urban health and estimate indicator values for health determinants such as unattractive views, heat stress, air pollution, perceived unsafety and tick-bite risk. Manfra et al., 2022 used an Artificial Intelligence (AI) method, Classification and Regression Trees (CART) to analyze datasets of tree failure, while Caggiu et al., 2023 used a multiple regression model to assess the risk potential of tree failure in urban trees. Ala-Hulkko et al., 2019, used a MaxEnt model which is a maximum entropy model developed for species distribution modelling based on presence-only prediction, to model tick distribution and abundance. Additionally, Escobedo et al., 2018 used descriptive statistics and available geospatial data to determine if urban treescape, demographic, and socioeconomic variables were related to the incidence of homicides in Colombia.

Ala-Hulkko et al., 2019 von Döhren and Haase, 2022 highlighted GIS-based spatial accessibility analysis and readily available geospatial data as a valuable approach for assessing and evaluating exposure risk of harmful EDS. Jombo et al., 2020, underscored the effectiveness of high-resolution WorldView-2 satellite imagery and machine learning. Jombo et al., 2020, explored high-resolution WorldView-2 satellite imagery and machine learning algorithms such as Random-forest (RF) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) for mapping urban tree species which will provide an insight into the municipality's urban forest and environmental managers in monitoring a region's urban tree species. Juanita et al., 2019; Potgieter et al., 2019a analyzed the impact of land use changes using satellite image classification and found that natural areas diminished as a result of rapid urbanisation and as a result of which ES are reducing while EDS increases in urban areas (Juanita et al., 2019) and areas invaded by alien invasive species along the urban edge

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7. Number of articles reviewed (n = 49): a) by continents b) by countries.

(Potgieter et al., 2019a; Caggiu et al., 2023 advocated for the use of open-source data among stakeholders for the management of urban green spaces.

3.3.3. Sampling method

3 studies utilized sampling methods, with 2 of them focusing specifically on pollen allergies in urban environments. Gharbi et al., 2023 used a 7-day Hirst-type volumetric trap to find that pollen grains emitted in urban areas significantly contribute to allergic reactions, and highlighting the importance of understanding and managing this environmental health concern. Similarly, Ćwik et al., 2021 conducted aerobiological monitoring. Their approach involved systematic sampling and monitoring to capture variations in pollen distribution and allergenic potential across different urban landscapes. Both Gharbi et al., 2023; Ćwik et al., 2021 advocate for integrating aerobiological criteria into urban green space planning to mitigate allergic impacts and enhance the aesthetic and recreational value of urban environments.

Yildirim et al., 2022 conducted measurements to understand the sound and noise associated with green and blue infrastructure. Sound measurements were collected at various sampling points within these

study areas, providing insight into the auditory EDS present in different environmental contexts.

3.3.4. Mixed-methods approach

Total 16 reviewed papers employed this approach using a combination of qualitative and quantitative analyses within a single study or across sequential phases.

Speak and Salbitano, 2021 exemplified the application of qualitative analysis through structured questionnaires designed to discern residents' perceptions regarding the benefits and drawbacks of urban trees. Concurrently, remote sensing and GIS were deployed to assess vegetation conditions and microclimate dynamics using vegetative indices, thereby enriching their qualitative findings with quantitative spatial data. Similarly, Koyata et al., 2021 adopted a mixed-methods strategy involving both qualitative (questionnaire) and modelling approach to examine the connections between environmental factors and socio-demographic variables, and community responses towards street trees. Plieninger et al., 2013 performed a questionnaire, participatory mapping and statistical analyses to analyze the complete range of cultural ES and EDS perceived by people.

Table 3

Characteristics of case study cities in reviewed articles (area and population according to Worldometer elaboration of the latest United Nations data and World Population Review).

Continent	City (State, Country)	Area size (km ²)	Population (inhabitants in 2024)
Europe	Berlin, Germany	891 km ²	3,576,873
	Bologna, Italy	140.9 km ²	366,133
	Bolzano, Italy	52.3 km ²	99,049
	Bucharest, Romania	228 km ²	1,767,520
	Florence, Italy	102.4 km ²	349,296
	Gutttau, Saxony, Germany	19.5 km ²	1760
	Heidelberg, Germany	108.8 km ²	179,995
	Karlsruhe, Germany	173.3 km ²	323,056
	Kristianstad, Sweden	21.4 km ²	39,762
	Maastricht, Netherlands	60.06 km ²	122,378
	Mahilioŭ, Belarus	118.5 km ²	369,200
	Malmö, Sweden	156.9 km ²	341,457
	Moscow, Russia	2511 km ²	12,712,305
	Naples, Italy	117.3 km ²	959,470
	Örebro, Sweden	49.27 km ²	115,765
	Rzeszów, Poland	120.4 km ²	158,382
	Settlements around Scarpe-Escaut Regional Natural Park, France	430 km ²	200,000
	Stuttgart, Germany	207.7 km ²	636,150
	St. Austell, Cornwall, UK	3.56 km ²	20,900
	Tampere, Finland	689.6 km ²	202,687
Turku, Finland	306.36 km ²	175,945	
Viterbo, Italy	406.3 km ²	70,563	
Asia	Beijing, China	16,410 km ²	22,189,082
	Bengaluru, India	741 km ²	5,104,047
	Bursa, Turkey	1290 km ²	2,115,513
	Calamba, Philippines	149.5 km ²	316,612
	Can Tho, Vietnam	1402 km ²	1,938,915
	Hong Kong, China	1110 km ²	7,012,738
	Nagoya, Japan	326.4 km ²	2,191,279
	Singapore	719.1 km ²	3,547,809
	Srinagar, India	294 km ²	975,857
	Taipei City, Taiwan	271.7 km ²	2,766,334
Tokyo, Japan	2194 km ²	37,115,035	
Yokohama, Japan	437.4 km ²	3,574,443	
Africa	Cape town, South Africa	2445 km ²	4,977,833
	Johannesburg, South Africa	1645 km ²	6,324,351
North America	Outjo, Namibia	97.9 km ²	6557
	Bala Cynwyd (suburb of Philadelphia), Pennsylvania, USA	6.99 km ²	9285
South America	Chicago, Illinois, USA	600 km ²	2,638,159
	Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, USA	369.59 km ²	1,533,828
South America	Syracuse, New York, USA	66 km ²	145,171
	Barranquilla Metropolitan Area, Colombia	477 km ²	2,373,302
	Bogota, Colombia	1587 km ²	7,674,366
	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil	1204 km ²	13,824,347

Table 3 (continued)

Continent	City (State, Country)	Area size (km ²)	Population (inhabitants in 2024)
Australia	São Paulo, Brazil	1523 km ²	22,806,704
	Central Coast local government area (LGA), New South Wales, Australia	1681 km ²	346,596
	Christchurch, New Zealand	1426 km ²	407,503
	Perth, Australia	1640 km ²	2,143,491
	Sydney, Australia	12,145 km ²	5,184,896

Drew-Smythe et al., 2023, Baltazar et al., 2022; Campagne et al., 2018 employed a blend of qualitative analysis (questionnaire) and statistical analyses to explore diverse aspects of EDS. Drew-Smythe et al., 2023 focused on assessing risks associated with falling branches and infrastructure damage from root systems, while Baltazar et al., 2022 delved into socio-cultural valuation (SCV) of ES and EDS to determine if ES outweighs EDS according to residents, and Campagne et al., 2018 examined correlations between ES and EDS within urban contexts. Drillet et al., 2020, Hui and Jim, 2022, Pistón et al., 2022; Thapa et al., 2023 extended this approach, to explore public perception of urban forests and street trees, and assess if EDS vary with the type of green infrastructure. Toledo-Gallegos et al., 2022 utilized a discrete choice experiment (DCE) survey method to quantify preferences for the ES and EDS provided by green and blue infrastructure (GBI). Wu et al., 2021 used this method to firstly propose a framework to improve the general understanding of the formation and types of EDS and then tried to valuate the costs caused by EDS, such as decrease in water quantity and infrastructure damage caused by growth of plants on infrastructures such as street pavement.

Azmy et al., 2016 utilized a combination of sampling methods, remote sensing (specifically vegetative indices) and statistical analyses to assess hornet abundance and associated risks of hornet bites, illustrating the integrated use of qualitative and quantitative approaches in ecological research. Masini et al., 2023; Hanford et al., 2019 employed similar mixed methods to analyze disservices caused by street trees and measure the abundance and diversity of mosquitoes in wetlands.

Finally, Speak et al., 2022 explored citizen participatory methods, involving students and diverse stakeholders such as city planners and architects, to envision and shape future urban landscapes collaboratively. This inclusive approach not only enriched data collection but also fostered community engagement and empowered stakeholders to contribute meaningfully to urban planning.

4. Discussion

An ever-growing number of EDS-related publications highlights an increasing effort to integrate EDS studies alongside ES within urban contexts. While ES are often highlighted, maintaining the status quo without addressing EDS can exacerbate environmental and societal impacts (Schaubroeck, 2017; Van Oijstaeijen et al., 2020). Most of the reviewed papers feature studies that assess EDS by examining the trade-offs and synergies between ES and EDS. While such studies can be lacking a clear focus on understanding the nature of EDS and their implications for complex urban planning management setups, they still represent a welcome addition to the EDS literature at this early stage of its development, and also demonstrate a somewhat holistic perspective by capturing both positive (ES) and negative (EDS) aspects of urban nature. This enhances our understanding of important socio-ecological interactions (Wu et al., 2021) and highlights the positive net benefit of urban ecosystems on human well-being (Schaubroeck, 2017).

Importantly, none of the reviewed studies had sufficiently elaborated on the conceptual foundations of EDS studies, such as understanding of the gradient between ES and EDS dimensions of ecosystems and

Table 4
Ecosystem disservices described in the reviewed papers (grouped after Skryhan and Shkaruba, 2022).

EDS group	Category	EDS types	References
I. Ecosystem attributes and functions	Ecosystem and its elements	Invasive species	(Potgieter et al., 2019a, 2019b; Sheergojri et al., 2022; Speak and Salbitano, 2021; Vaz et al., 2017; Yam et al., 2015)
		Tree failure (Risks of old trees and branches falling)	(Caggiu et al., 2023; Drew-Smythe et al., 2023; Hui and Jim, 2022; Koyata et al., 2021; Manfra et al., 2022; Masini et al., 2023; Roman et al., 2021; Speak et al., 2022)
	Functioning of urban green and blue spaces (UGBS)	Cracking pavements from wandering tree roots	(Manfra et al., 2022; Masini et al., 2023; Pistón et al., 2022; Stoia et al., 2022)
		Nuisances from plant/tree litter	(Koyata et al., 2021; Roman et al., 2021; Stoia et al., 2022)
		Car staining caused by tree fruits	Stoia et al. (2022)
		Infrastructure damage	(Baumeister et al., 2022; Campagne et al., 2018; Drew-Smythe et al., 2023; Drillet et al., 2020; Roman et al., 2021; Speak et al., 2022; Speak and Salbitano, 2021; Wu et al., 2021)
		Bio-emissions by plants/dust/air pollution	(Ignatieva et al., 2020; Oosterbroek et al., 2024; Roman et al., 2021; Shah et al., 2023; Speak and Salbitano, 2021)
		Deterioration in water quality	(Wood et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2021)
		Harmful algal bloom	Willis et al. (2018)
		Allergies and diseases	(Artmann et al., 2017; Campagne et al., 2018; Ćwik et al., 2021; Drew-Smythe et al., 2023; Gharbi et al., 2023; Hui and Jim, 2022; Juanita et al., 2019; Prigioniero et al., 2022; Speak and Salbitano, 2021; Stoia et al., 2022; von Döhren and Haase, 2022)
II. Human health	Risks related to human health	Tick-bite risk	(Ala-Hulkko et al., 2019; Oosterbroek et al., 2023)
		Snake-bite risk	(Hwang and Roscoe, 2017; Thapa et al., 2023)
	Nature related fears	Human-wildlife interaction	(Azmy et al., 2016; Campagne et al., 2018; Eriksson et al., 2020; Hosaka et al., 2017; Juanita et al., 2019; König et al., 2021; Luetkemeier

Table 4 (continued)

EDS group	Category	EDS types	References		
III. Aesthetic issues	Wild nature objects perceived as ugly and/or unpleasant due to our aesthetic, cultural, religious or other values and beliefs	Social unsafety/insecurity	et al., 2023; Thapa et al., 2023) (Baumeister et al., 2022; Oosterbroek et al., 2023)		
		Fear of darkness	Juanita et al. (2019)		
		Presence of insects/pests	(Campagne et al., 2018; Drillet et al., 2020; Juanita et al., 2019; Koyata et al., 2021; Stoia et al., 2022; Toledo-Gallegos et al., 2022)		
		Mosquito risk	(Hanford et al., 2019; Hwang and Roscoe, 2017; Shah et al., 2023)		
		Loud noise associated with UGS	(Baumeister et al., 2022; Belaire et al., 2015; Juanita et al., 2019; Yildirim et al., 2022)		
		Unattractive view/unmanaged and unpleasant/dirty	(Drillet et al., 2020; Ignatieva et al., 2020; Oosterbroek et al., 2023; Pistón et al., 2022; Plieninger et al., 2013; Skryhan and Shkaruba, 2022; Speak et al., 2022)		
		Nuisances like open defecation/dumping of garbage/sewage	(Baumeister et al., 2022; Thapa et al., 2023)		
		Restricted access	Baumeister et al. (2022)		
		IV. Restrictions and inhibition of urban planning and development	Restrictions caused by nature protection Inhibition of activities	Crimes associated with UGS	(Baltazar et al., 2022; Baumeister et al., 2022; Escobedo et al., 2018; Hui and Jim, 2022; Hwang and Roscoe, 2017; Oosterbroek et al., 2023; Pistón et al., 2022)
				Anti-social activities like alcohol/drug consumption	(Plieninger et al., 2013; Thapa et al., 2023)
Dense vegetation blocking view	Baumeister et al. (2022)				

biodiversity. Yet such a gradient is clearly recognized and being investigated (Toledo-Gallegos et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2021). More papers lay crisp boundaries between the EDS associated with human-caused ecosystem degradation, and the impacts causing such degradation (such as plastic pollution, urban pollution from synthetic lawns, air pollution from traffic or water contamination from open dumping) (Ignatieva et al., 2020; Oosterbroek et al., 2023; Saunders, 2020b; Wood et al., 2022). This already represents an important step towards the understanding EDS in their ecological and socio-cultural context.

4.1. Evaluation methods of EDS

In terms of the methods mostly used to study ES, combinations of quantitative and qualitative approaches appear to be most common, followed by quantitative methods, encompassing a broad range of methodologies (Kosanic and Petzold, 2020; Nápoles-Vértiz and Caro-Borrero, 2024). In contrast, research on EDS has primarily been conducted through opinion papers and qualitative analyses, such as

Table 5
Types of Ecosystem Disservices spread across geographically as seen in reviewed articles.

Continent	Ecosystem Disservices (EDS)	City (State, Country)
Europe	Allergies and diseases	Berlin, Germany; Bolzano, Naples, Italy; Bucharest, Romania; Rzeszów, Poland; Stuttgart, Karlsruhe, & Heilderberg; Germany, Settlements around Scarpe-Escaut Regional Natural Park, France
	Anti-social activities like alcohol/drug consumption	Guttau, Saxony, Germany
	Bio-emissions by plants/dust/air pollution	Bolzano, Italy; Maastricht, Netherlands; Moscow, Russia
	Dense vegetation blocking view	Stuttgart, Karlsruhe, & Heilderberg; Germany
	Cracking pavements from wandering tree roots	Bucharest, Romania; Viterbo, Italy
	Crimes associated with UGS	Maastricht, Netherlands; Stuttgart, Karlsruhe, & Heilderberg; Germany United Kingdom
	Deterioration in water quality	
	Harmful algal bloom	St Austell, Cornwall, United Kingdom
	Human-wildlife interaction	Berlin, Germany; Kristianstad and Örebro, Sweden; Settlements around Scarpe-Escaut Regional Natural Park, France;
	Infrastructure damage	Bolzano & Florence, Italy; Settlements around Scarpe-Escaut Regional Natural Park, France; Stuttgart, Karlsruhe, & Heilderberg; Germany
	Invasive species	Florence, Italy; Stuttgart, Karlsruhe, & Heilderberg; Germany
	Loud noise associated with UGS	Stuttgart, Karlsruhe, & Heilderberg; Germany
	Nuisances from plant/tree litter	Bucharest, Romania; Malmö, Sweden
	Nuisances like open defecation/dumping of garbage/sewage	Stuttgart, Karlsruhe, & Heilderberg; Germany
	Car staining caused by tree fruits	Bucharest, Romania
	Presence of insects/pests	Bucharest, Romania; Settlements around Scarpe-Escaut Regional Natural Park, France
	Restricted Access	Stuttgart, Karlsruhe, & Heilderberg; Germany
	Social unsafety/insecurity	Maastricht, Netherlands; Stuttgart, Karlsruhe, & Heilderberg; Germany
	Tick-bite risk	Maastricht, Netherlands; Tampere and Turku, Finland
	Asia	Tree failure (Risk of old tree/branches falling)
Unattractive, unmanaged and unpleasant sites		Bolzano, Italy, Florence, Italy; Guttau, Saxony, Germany; Maastricht, The Netherlands; Moscow, Russia; Mahiliou, Belarus
Allergies and diseases		Hong Kong, China
Anti-social activities like alcohol/drug consumption		Bengaluru, India
Bio-emissions by plants/dust/air pollution		Beijing, China
Crimes associated with UGS		Calamba, Philippines, Hong Kong, China and Singapore
Deterioration in water quality		Beijing, China
Human-wildlife interaction		Beijing, China; Bengaluru, India; Nagoya, Tokyo, Japan
Infrastructure damage		Beijing, China; Singapore
Invasive species		Srinagar, India and Taipei, Taiwan
Loud noise associated with UGS	Bursa City, Turkey	
Mosquito risk	Beijing, China and Singapore	

Table 5 (continued)

Continent	Ecosystem Disservices (EDS)	City (State, Country)
South America	Nuisances from plant/tree litter	Yokohama, Japan
	Nuisances like open defecation/dumping of garbage/sewage	Bengaluru, India
	Presence of insects/pests	Can Tho, Vietnam; Yokohama, Japan, Singapore
	Snake-bite risk	Bengaluru, India; Singapore
	Tree failure	Yokohama, Japan
	Unattractive, unmanaged and unpleasant sites	Hong Kong, China; Singapore; Yokohama, Japan
	Allergies and diseases	Barranquilla Metropolitan Area, Colombia
	Cracking pavements from wandering tree roots	Rio de Janeiro & São Paulo, Brazil
	Crimes associated with UGS	Bogota, Colombia and Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
	Fear of darkness	Barranquilla Metropolitan Area, Colombia
	Human-wildlife interaction	Barranquilla Metropolitan Area, Colombia
	Presence of insects/pests	Barranquilla Metropolitan Area, Colombia
	Tree failure	São Paulo, Brazil
	Unattractive, unmanaged and unpleasant sites	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
	North America	Bio-emissions by plants/dust/air pollution
Infrastructure damage		Chicago, Illinois, USA
Nuisances from plant/tree litter		Chicago, Pennsylvania, USA
Tree failure		Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, USA
Unattractive, unmanaged and unpleasant sites		Syracuse, New York, USA
Africa	Allergies and diseases	Johannesburg & Cape Town, South Africa
	Cracking pavements from wandering tree roots	Randburg, Johannesburg, South Africa
	Human-wildlife interaction	Outjo, Kunene region, Namibia
	Invasive species	Cape town, South Africa
	Allergies and diseases	New South Wales, Australia
Australia and Oceania	Bio-emissions by plants/dust/air pollution	Christchurch, New Zealand
	Infrastructure damage	New South Wales, Australia
	Mosquito risk	Sydney, Australia
	Tree failure	New South Wales, Australia
	Unattractive, unmanaged and unpleasant sites	Christchurch, New Zealand

social perception studies using questionnaires and interviews (Blanco et al., 2019; Saunders, 2020b). These qualitative methods are often employed to compare and analyze citizens' perspectives on urban nature. Quantification, along with qualitative approaches involving stakeholders, are key elements for ES assessment impacting policies (Zolyomi et al., 2023). This highlights a significant gap in the field of EDS, calling for researchers to focus more on the quantification of EDS that is significantly less mature than ES as a concept.

Mapping and quantitative assessment of ES involves remote sensing data and geographical information system (GIS) software, monetary valuation methods, ecosystem services modelling method like InVEST for mapping and evaluating ecological or economic value of numerous ES as well as multicriteria decision analysis (MCDA) that explicitly account for numerous criteria in assisting people or groups in making important choices. GIS is used to carry out spatial MCDA to visualize the various standards. (Remme et al., 2021; Sharma et al; Zolyomi et al., 2023). While monetary methods have long been used to value ES (Sharma et al), only two out of the reviewed papers have tried to evaluate the costs loss caused by EDS (Roman et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2021). Additionally, Spatial Modelling approaches have been used in ES studies to determine the supply (and demand) of different ES (Sharma et al)

Fig. 8. Ecosystem disservices featured in reviewed papers.

Fig. 9. Evaluation methods used to study ecosystem disservices in reviewed articles.

while in EDS, Remote Sensing and GIS has only confined to mapping street trees causing different EDS, areas with invasive species, neglected, degraded and unpleasant sites as well as tick distribution and abundance (Ala-Hulkko et al., 2019; Baumeister et al., 2022; Juanita et al., 2019; Manfra et al., 2022; Plieninger et al., 2013; Potgieter et al., 2019a). Unlike ES, EDS is not recognized by politically-endorsed framework, such as the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA), The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity (TEEB) and the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) (Sharma et al), and nor streamlined into policies and planning practices. This underlines the need for either rethinking EDS in the terms that are compatible with ES assessment methodologies, or the development of

EDS-specific quantitative frameworks.

Based on the evidence provided in the review, a clear call can be recognized for more quantification of EDS, as well as integration of EDS study in ES assessment frameworks, policy-making and also in urban planning practices. This comprehensive approach will ensure a balanced understanding of urban ecosystems, leading to more effective and equitable urban green management strategies and more inclusive urban planning.

4.2. Geographical distribution of EDS studies

The review demonstrates an uneven geographical coverage of EDS

Table 6
Summary of different evaluation methods used in 49 reviewed papers.

Evaluation methods		
Approaches/ methods	Methods/Data used	References
Qualitative analyses	Framework like FoPIA, SEEDS and 3i	König et al. (2021)
	Focus Group Discussions (FGDs)	Sheergojri et al. (2022)
	Interviews	(Luetkemeier et al., 2023; Skryhan and Shkaruba, 2022; Willis et al., 2018)
	Integrated Participatory qualitative approach	Oosterbroek et al. (2024)
Literature mining		(Ignatieva et al., 2020; Roman et al., 2021; Shah et al., 2023; Vaz et al., 2017; Yam et al., 2015)
	Questionnaire	(Artmann et al., 2017; Belaïre et al., 2015; Eriksson et al., 2020; Hosaka et al., 2017; Hwang and Roscoe, 2017; Potgieter et al., 2019b; Stoia et al., 2022; Wood et al., 2022)
Remote Sensing and GIS	Generalized linear model (GLM) using geo-referenced homicide and treescape data	Escobedo et al. (2018)
	i-Tree Eco model.	Prigioniero et al. (2022)
	Landsat TM + and OLI/TIRS satellite data	Juanita et al. (2019)
	LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) data and multispectral imagery	(Oosterbroek et al., 2023; Potgieter et al., 2019a)
	Maxent (maximum entropy model) based on presence-only data	Ala-Hulkko et al. (2019)
	Open-source geospatial raster data provided by the geodatabase of the administration of the city	(Caggiu et al., 2023; von Döhren and Haase, 2022)
Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method		Manfra et al. (2022)
	Public Participatory GIS (PPGIS) mapping	Baumeister et al. (2022)
Sampling method	Worldview-2 imagery	Jombo et al. (2020)
	Airborne pollen sampling	(Ćwik et al., 2021; Gharbi et al., 2023)
Mixed-method analyses	Sound sampling	Yildirim et al. (2022)
	Qualitative online survey + i-Tree Eco methodology	Speak et al. (2022)
	Qualitative analyses + Monetary valuation (conventional and implicit markets, actual behaviors-based valuation methods, intended behavior-based valuation method and choice experiment methods	Wu et al. (2021)
	Questionnaire + discreet choice experiment	Toledo-Gallegos et al. (2022)
	Questionnaire + Ordinal logit regression model	Koyata et al. (2021)
	Questionnaire + Vegetative Indices using Multi-spectral satellite	Speak and Salbitano (2021)
	Data from the Sentinel-2 platform	
	Questionnaire + Spatial mapping using ArcGIS 9.3 + Statistical analyses (hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA) and multiple correspondence analysis (MCA)) using PASW (SPSS) 18, Excel 2003 and XSLSTAT 2012.4.01	Plieninger et al. (2013)

Table 6 (continued)

Evaluation methods		
Approaches/ methods	Methods/Data used	References
	Questionnaire + Statistical analyses (Chi-squared tests, Friedman's test, G test, Kruskal-Wallis test, Principal component analysis (PCA), Wilcoxon signed-rank test)	(Baltazar et al., 2022; Campagne et al., 2018; Drew-Smythe et al., 2023; Drillet et al., 2020; Hui and Jim, 2022; Pistón et al., 2022; Thapa et al., 2023)
	Sampling + Vegetative Indices using Landsat 8 data + Statistical analysis using Spearman's rank correlation and Bray-Curtis method	Azmy et al. (2016)
	Sampling + Statistical analysis (Permutational multivariate analysis of variance (PERMANOVA), Canonical Analysis of Principal Components (CAP) and correlation analysis)	(Hanford et al., 2019; Masini et al., 2023)

case studies, whereas most of literature originates from Europe (21 locations out of 48 featuring in the reviewed pool). 34 cases come from OECD countries that further underlines geographical asymmetries, arguably due to greater emphasis in such countries on urban nature and nature-based solutions like the OECD Green Growth Strategy (Hickel and Kallis, 2020), and the prioritization of such research topics by funding agencies (Calliari et al., 2022). Potentially, EDS also can be recognized there as a more pertinent problem for the citizens. This can be the case because more basic components of good urban living, such as housing quality, water supply and sanitation, road maintenance, pollution, safety and so on, have been largely addressed in OECD countries (Tonne et al., 2021), unlike many non-OECD ones. This observation again reminds that EDS is a very much socio-cultural construct, as long as most OECD countries are located in temperate climates where nature is normally more curated (or less aggressive, in more direct terms) than in mostly tropical non-OECD countries found in the pool of reviewed cases.

In terms of the character of analyzed EDS, the comparison of OECD vs. non-OECD countries shows little difference: out of 24 EDS types 20 were described in OECD and 15 in non-OECD countries that however can be attributed to less developed EDS research in the latter. There are four EDS types, which are present in papers coming from the non-OECD area and absent in the OECD: 'Nuisances like open defecation/dumping of garbage/sewage', 'Car staining caused by tree fruits', 'Presence of insects/pests' and 'Snake-bite risk' (Baumeister et al., 2022; Campagne et al., 2018; Hwang and Roscoe, 2017; Stoia et al., 2022).

The same kind of comparison between the cases located in temperate (including Arctic) and tropical (including subtropical) climatic zones has demonstrated slightly more significant deviations. Out of 24 EDS types, 20 have been described for temperate and 13 for tropical locations, with the following three described only for the tropics – 'Fear of darkness', 'Nuisances like open defecation/dumping of garbage/sewage' and 'Snake-bite risk' darkness' (Baumeister et al., 2022; Hwang and Roscoe, 2017; Juanita et al., 2019), and the following eleven only in the temperate zone – 'Blocked road view', 'Deterioration in water quality', 'Dust/Air pollution', 'Harmful algal blooms', 'Infrastructure damage', 'Loud noise associated with UGS', 'Nuisances from plant/tree litter', 'Car staining caused by tree fruits', 'Restricted Access to green areas', 'Social unsafety/insecurity', 'Tick-bite risk' (Baumeister et al., 2022; Belaïre et al., 2015; Campagne et al., 2018; Drillet et al., 2020; Drew-Smythe et al., 2023; Ignatieva et al., 2020; Juanita et al., 2019; Koyata et al., 2021; Oosterbroek et al., 2023, 2024; Roman et al., 2021; Shah et al., 2023; Speak et al., 2022; Speak and Salbitano, 2021; Stoia et al., 2022; Willis et al., 2018; Wood et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2021;

Yildirim et al., 2022). While this difference in analyzed disservices types can be partly attributed to still greater interest in EDS by institutions from temperate climate locations, some geographical patterns emerge even from these simple comparisons, especially those associated with the biogeography: greater presence of larger wild animals and venomous snakes is clearly more typical for tropical locations (Hwang and Roscoe, 2017; Thapa et al., 2023), while tick bites is a problem of green areas in the temperate zone (Ala-Hulkko et al., 2019; Oosterbroek et al., 2023).

4.3. Vulnerable groups are not in focus

Our review highlights a notable deficiency in research addressing the impacts of EDS on vulnerable groups, such as seniors, children, females and residents with health conditions. Only 3 papers out of the 49 had focus on vulnerable groups (Pistón et al., 2022; Stoia et al., 2022; von Döhren and Haase, 2022). For instance, a study by von Döhren and Haase (2022) reveals that children are particularly vulnerable to the effects of poisonous plants in urban green spaces due to their lack of knowledge about appropriate behavior towards unknown plants and their increased susceptibility to harmful substances as a result of their developmental state and metabolism. Similarly, Stoia et al., 2022 found that elderly people prefer public transport and shaded routes over walking and cycling along urban green spaces. Pistón et al., 2022 revealed that when questioned about negative aspects of street trees, female respondents were concerned with an EDS, ‘risk of crime’ whereas males recognized more ‘unattractive species’.

Vulnerability is a multifaceted condition that encompasses various socioeconomic, demographic, environmental, and health conditions. In the United States and European countries, vulnerability is frequently measured by socioeconomic status, demographics including age, housing condition, and access to health care while government health institutions in the Global South classify vulnerable populations based on characteristics such as ethnicity, gender, resource access, power dynamics, and being victims of armed conflict, in addition to sociodemographic factors (Escobedo et al., 2023). Understanding and quantifying EDS and environmental injustices in cities, marked by strong inequalities and contrasting socioecological realities is key to comprehending inequity, exclusion and systematic racism and can highly impact environmental policies, healthcare sectors and urban planning strategies (Escobedo et al., 2023; Pistón et al., 2022; Remme et al., 2021). It is therefore crucial to understand the impact of different EDS on the wellbeing of various social and vulnerable groups spread across geographically as well as utilize different assessment methods that reveal how ecosystem changes can influence the flow and values of ES to different beneficiaries across landscapes (Remme et al., 2021) in order to implement inclusive urban planning strategies and policies.

4.4. Limitations and future directions

Some findings of this review should be approached with caution due to several limitations. Firstly, the review is based solely on peer-reviewed literature focusing on EDS in urban settings, which may not fully capture the broad contributions of the scientific community. Secondly, the reviewed studies mostly addressed both ES and EDS, indicating a scarcity of research focused solely on EDS. This can dilute the attention given to specific complexities of disservices. Thirdly, the review is centered around the term ‘ecosystem disservices’ and includes only studies that explicitly use this term, potentially excluding relevant research that uses different terminology. Fourthly, the review is limited to English-language publications, which may overlook significant studies published in other languages. Furthermore, the analysis relied exclusively on the Web of Science database and results might vary if other databases such as Scopus or PubMed were included.

The relatively small number of identified articles further implies that the findings should not be considered a definitive categorization of EDS

and their relationships. Instead, they should be regarded as a preliminary framework for organizing the connections between EDS and urban socio-ecological systems, the studies conducted, and the assessment methods employed, but further studies are required to refine this framework and enhance its applicability to urban planning and management. Moreover, further research could explore a wider range of keywords, as well as more references, geographical locations, languages and ecological contexts to fill the gaps and provide a more holistic perspective on EDS.

5. Conclusion

This systematic literature review (SLR) explores the emerging field of ecosystem disservices (EDS) in urban environments, examining the nature and distribution of EDS across various sociocultural and economic regions, as well as the methodologies used to study them, highlighting the need for a balanced understanding of both ES and EDS in urban planning and policy development. By combining qualitative reading of the articles and bibliometric analysis, this study presents a comprehensive overview of the state of research on EDS and serves as an initial framework to understanding the EDS concept. While the concept of ES has been widely integrated into urban management frameworks, EDS remains underdeveloped, despite its growing significance in capturing the full complexity of urban ecosystems. This review has shown that while much of the available literature focuses on qualitative assessments, there is a notable gap in quantitative approaches that would provide evidence-based methods and enable a more robust integration of EDS into urban planning, policy, and decision-making.

The qualitative analysis of the review revealed a predominant geographical focus on European cities in OECD countries (mostly in Europe), highlighting the need for more extensive and diverse studies, region-specific research, particularly in the global South, to better understand the socio-cultural and geographical dimensions of EDS across various urban contexts. Additionally, the EDS types mentioned fails to adequately address the intersection between EDS and key social issues like, economic inequality, housing challenges, and the dynamics of green gentrification, which can significantly influence urban planning and management. Moreover, the impact of EDS on vulnerable populations such as children, the elderly, and individuals with pre-existing health conditions remains an underexplored area, indicating the need for more inclusive research that considers social inequalities and environmental justice in urban ecosystems.

The findings therefore suggest that future research must focus on the development of standardized quantitative methods for assessing EDS, with an emphasis on integrating these studies within ES frameworks. Moreover, further attention should be paid to the socio-cultural dimensions of EDS. Addressing these gaps will not only enhance our understanding of the complexities of human-nature interactions in urban settings but also serve as a basis for urban planners and policy-makers towards developing more equitable, sustainable, and effective urban planning strategies. By advancing the study of EDS, cities can better manage the dual nature of urban greenery – its services as well as its disservices, leading to healthier, more resilient and inclusive urban environments for all urban residents.

In conclusion, integration of EDS into urban research, planning and policy frameworks, is critical for fostering more holistic, inclusive and sustainable cities. As our understanding of EDS continues to evolve, it is crucial that future research moves beyond qualitative and focuses on the development of quantitative study, methods and policy interventions that address both the positive and negative aspects of urban ecosystems.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ruthi Veibiakkim: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Anton Shkaruba:** Writing – review & editing, Validation,

Supervision, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Kalev Sepp:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A

Table A.1
Overview of Ecosystem Disservices case studies found in literature

Ecosystem Disservices (EDS)			Region		Approaches/methods	References		
<i>EDS group</i>	<i>Sub group</i>	<i>Types</i>	<i>Ecosystem type</i>	<i>Town/City/Country</i>				
I. Ecosystem attributes and functions	Ecosystem and its element	<i>Invasive species</i>	Urban Residential Area (URA)	Cape town, South Africa	Remote sensing and GIS	Potgieter et al. (2019a)		
			Urban Freshwater Lake	Srinagar, India	Qualitative analysis (Questionnaire/ interview)	Sheergojri et al. (2022)		
			Urban Green Space (UGS)	Florence, Italy	Mixed method approach (Questionnaire + Remote sensing and GIS)	Speak and Salbitano (2021)		
			Urban Wetlands	Taipei, Taiwan	Qualitative analysis (literature mining)	Yam et al. (2015)		
			URA	Cape Town, South Africa	Qualitative analysis	(Potgieter et al., 2019b; Vaz et al., 2017)		
			Functioning of UGBS	<i>Tree failure; risks of old trees and branches falling</i>	URA	Bologna, Italy	Remote Sensing and GIS	Caggiu et al. (2023)
					UGS	New South Wales, Australia	Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Drew-Smythe et al. (2023)
					UGS	Hong Kong, China	Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Hui and Jim (2022)
					URA	Yokohama, Japan	Mixed-method approach (Questionnaire + Modelling)	Koyata et al. (2021)
	URA	Sao Paulo, Brazil			Remote Sensing and GIS (Artificial intelligence model)	Manfra et al. (2022)		
	URA	Viterbo, Italy			Mixed-method approach (Sampling + statistical analysis)	Masini et al. (2023)		
	UGS	Bala Cynwyd, Pennsylvania, USA			Qualitative analysis	Roman et al. (2021)		
	UGS	Bolzano, Italy			Mixed-method approach (Qualitative online survey + participatory approach)	Speak et al. (2022)		
	<i>Cracking pavements and foundations due to wandering tree roots</i>	URA			Sao Paulo, Brazil	Remote Sensing and GIS (Artificial Intelligence model)	Manfra et al. (2022)	
		URA	Viterbo, Italy	Mixed-method approach (Sampling + Statistical analysis)	Masini et al. (2023)			
		Urban Parks	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil	Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Pistón et al. (2022)			
		URA	Randburg, Johannesburg, South Africa	Remote sensing and GIS	Jombo et al. (2020)			
		<i>Nuisances from plant/tree litter</i>	URA	Yokohama, Japan	Mixed-method approach (Questionnaire + Modelling)	Koyata et al. (2021)		
UGS			Malmö, Sweden	Qualitative analysis	Roman et al. (2021)			
	Urban parks	Bucharest, Romania	Qualitative (Questionnaire)	Stoia et al. (2022)				

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Table A.1 (continued)

Ecosystem Disservices (EDS)			Region		Approaches/methods	References
EDS group	Sub group	Types	Ecosystem type	Town/City/Country		
II. Human health	Risks related to human health	Pavement or car staining caused by falling fruits Infrastructure damage	Urban Parks	Bucharest, Romania	Qualitative (Questionnaire)	Stoia et al. (2022)
			UGS	Stuttgart, Karlsruhe, & Heilderberg, Germany	Remote sensing and GIS (Participatory mapping)	Baumeister et al. (2022)
			Urban Parks	Scarpe-Escaut Regional Natural Park, France	Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Campagne et al. (2018)
			UGS	New South Wales, Australia	Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Drew-Smythe et al. (2023)
			Urban Forests	Singapore	Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Drillet et al. (2020)
			UGS	Malmö, Sweden	Qualitative analysis	Roman et al. (2021)
			UGS	Bolzano, Italy	Mixed method approach (Qualitative online survey + participatory approach)	Speak et al. (2022)
			UGS	Florence, Italy	Mixed method approach (Questionnaire + Remote sensing and GIS)	Speak and Salbitano (2021)
			UGS	Beijing, China	Mixed method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Wu et al. (2021)
			Bio-emissions by plants/dust/air pollution	Urban Lawns	Europe (Germany, Sweden and Russia), New Zealand (Christchurch), USA (Syracuse, NY) and Australia (Perth)	Qualitative analysis
		UGS		Maastricht, Netherlands	Qualitative analysis	Oosterbroek et al. (2024)
		UGS		Malmö, Sweden	Qualitative analysis	Roman et al. (2021)
		Urban Constructed Wetlands		Beijing, China	Qualitative Analysis (Literature mining)	Shah et al. (2023)
		UGS		Florence, Italy	Mixed method approach (Questionnaire + Remote sensing and GIS)	Speak and Salbitano (2021)
		Deterioration in water quality	Urban Blue Space (UBS)	United Kingdom	Qualitative analysis (Questionnaire)	Wood et al. (2022)
			UGS	Beijing, China	Mixed method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Wu et al. (2021)
		Harmful algal bloom	UGS	St Austell, Cornwall, United Kingdom	Qualitative approach (interviews/questionnaire)	Willis et al. (2018)
			UGS	Cities in Europe	Qualitative analysis	Artmann et al. (2017)
			Urban Parks	Scarpe-Escaut Regional Natural Park, France	Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Campagne et al. (2018)
			Urban Blue-Green Space (BGS)	Rzeszów, Poland	Sampling method	Ćwik et al. (2021)
UGS	New South Wales, Australia		Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Drew-Smythe et al. (2023)		
Urban Forests	Johannesburg and Cape Town, South Africa		Sampling method	Gharbi et al. (2023)		
UGS	Hong Kong, China		Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Hui and Jim (2022)		
Urban Landscape	Barranquilla Metropolitan Area, Colombia		Remote sensing and GIS	Juanita et al. (2019)		
Urban Forests	Naples, Italy		Remote Sensing and GIS	Prigioniero et al. (2022)		
UGS	Florence, Italy		Mixed method approach (Questionnaire + Remote sensing and GIS)	Speak and Salbitano (2021)		
Urban Parks	Bucharest, Romania		Qualitative (Questionnaire)	Stoia et al. (2022)		
UGS	Berlin, Germany		Remote Sensing and GIS	von Döhren and Haase (2022)		

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Table A.1 (continued)

Ecosystem Disservices (EDS)			Region		Approaches/methods	References		
EDS group	Sub group	Types	Ecosystem type	Town/City/Country				
III. Aesthetic issues	Wild nature objects perceived as ugly and/or unpleasant due to our aesthetic, cultural, religious or other values and beliefs	Dangerous diseases caused by ticks	URA	Tampere, Turku; Finland	Remote Sensing and GIS	Ala-Hulkko et al. (2019)		
			UGS	Maastricht, Netherlands	Remote Sensing and GIS	Oosterbroek et al. (2023)		
		Snake bite risk	Urban Forests	Singapore	Qualitative analysis (Questionnaire)	Hwang and Roscoe (2017)		
			UGS	Bengaluru, India	Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Thapa et al. (2023)		
		Nature related fears	Fear of human-wildlife interactions	UGS	Nagoya, Tokyo, Japan	Mixed-method approach (Sampling + Remote Sensing and GIS + Statistical analysis)	Azmy et al. (2016)	
				Urban Parks	Scarpe-Escaut Regional Natural Park, France	Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Campagne et al. (2018)	
				URA	Kristianstad and Örebro, Sweden	Qualitative analysis (Questionnaire)	Eriksson et al. (2020)	
				UGS	Tokyo, Japan	Qualitative analysis (Questionnaire/ interview)	Hosaka et al. (2017)	
				Urban Landscape	Barranquilla Metropolitan Area, Colombia	Remote sensing and GIS	Juanita et al. (2019)	
				Urban landscape	Berlin, Brandenburg, Germany	Qualitative analysis	König et al. (2021)	
				Urban Parks	Outjo, Kunene region, Namibia	Qualitative analysis	Luetkemeier et al. (2023)	
				UGS	Bengaluru, India	Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Thapa et al. (2023)	
				Social unsafety/insecurity	Urban forests	Stuttgart, Karlsruhe, & Heilderberg, Germany	Remote sensing and GIS (Participatory mapping)	Baumeister et al. (2022)
					UGS	Maastricht, Netherlands	Remote Sensing and GIS	Oosterbroek et al. (2023)
		Wild nature objects perceived as ugly and/or unpleasant due to our aesthetic, cultural, religious or other values and beliefs	Presence of insects/pests	Fear of darkness	Urban Landscape	Barranquilla Metropolitan Area, Colombia	Remote sensing and GIS	Juanita et al. (2019)
				Urban Parks	Scarpe-Escaut Regional Natural Park, France	Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Campagne et al. (2018)	
				Urban Forests	Singapore	Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Drillet et al. (2020)	
				Urban Landscape	Barranquilla Metropolitan Area, Colombia	Remote sensing and GIS	Juanita et al. (2019)	
				URA	Yokohama, Japan	Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Modelling)	Koyata et al. (2021)	
				Urban Parks	Bucharest, Romania	Qualitative (Questionnaire)	Stoia et al. (2022)	
				Urban BGS	Can Tho, Vietnam	Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Toledo-Gallegos et al. (2022)	
				Presence of mosquitoes	Urban Wetlands	Sydney, Australia	Mixed-method approach (Sampling + statistical analysis)	Hanford et al. (2019)
					Urban Forests	Singapore	Qualitative analysis (Questionnaire)	Hwang and Roscoe (2017)
Urban Constructed Wetlands	Beijing, China				Qualitative Analysis (Literature mining)	Shah et al. (2023)		
Loud noise associated with UGS	Urban Forests	Stuttgart, Karlsruhe, & Heilderberg, Germany	Remote sensing and GIS (Participatory mapping)	Baumeister et al. (2022)				
	URA	Cook county, Illinois, USA	Qualitative analysis	Belaire et al. (2015)				
	Urban Landscape	Barranquilla Metropolitan Area, Colombia	Remote sensing and GIS	Juanita et al. (2019)				
	Urban BGS	Bursa City, Turkey	Sampling method	Yildirim et al. (2022)				
Unattractive view/unmanaged and unpleasant/dirty	Urban Forests	Singapore	Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Drillet et al. (2020)				
	Urban Lawns	Europe (Germany, Sweden and Russia), New Zealand (Christchurch), USA	Qualitative analysis	Ignatieva et al. (2020)				

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Table A.1 (continued)

Ecosystem Disservices (EDS)			Region		Approaches/methods	References		
EDS group	Sub group	Types	Ecosystem type	Town/City/Country				
IV. Restrictions and inhibition of urban planning and development	Restrictions caused by nature protection Inhibition of activities	Nuisances like open defecation/dumping of garbage/sewage Restricted access Crimes associated with UGS Anti-social activities like alcohol/drug consumption Dense vegetation blocking view	UGS	(Syracuse, NY) and Australia (Perth)	Remote Sensing and GIS	Oosterbroek et al. (2023) Pistón et al. (2022)		
			Urban Parks	Maastricht (The Netherlands)				
			Urban Parks	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil			Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	
			Urban Landscape	Gutttau, Saxony, Germany			Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Remote sensing and GIS)	Plieninger et al. (2013)
			Urban Landscape	Mahiliou, Belarus			Qualitative Analysis	Skryhan and Shkaruba (2022)
			UGS	Florence, Italy			Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Remote sensing and GIS)	Speak and Salbitano (2021)
			Urban Forests	Stuttgart, Karlsruhe, & Heilderberg, Germany			Remote sensing and GIS (Participatory mapping)	Baumeister et al. (2022)
			UGS	Bengaluru, India			Mixed-method approach (Questionnaire + Statistical analysis)	Thapa et al. (2023)
			Urban Forests	Stuttgart, Karlsruhe, & Heilderberg, Germany			Remote sensing and GIS (Participatory mapping)	Baumeister et al. (2022)
			Urban Parks	Calamba, Philippines			Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Baltazar et al. (2022)
			Urban Forests	Stuttgart, Karlsruhe, & Heilderberg, Germany			Remote sensing and GIS (Participatory mapping)	Baumeister et al. (2022)
			URA	Bogota, Colombia			Remote Sensing and GIS	Escobedo et al. (2018)
			UGS	Hong Kong			Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Hui and Jim (2022)
			Urban Forests	Singapore			Qualitative Analysis (Questionnaire)	Hwang and Roscoe (2017)
			UGS	Maastricht, Netherlands			Remote Sensing and GIS	Oosterbroek et al. (2023)
Urban Parks	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil	Mixed-method approach (Qualitative + Statistical analysis)	Pistón et al. (2022)					
Urban Landscape	Gutttau, Saxony, Germany	Remote Sensing and GIS (Qualitative + Remote sensing and GIS)	Plieninger et al. (2013)					
UGS	Bengaluru, India	Mixed-method approach (Questionnaire + Statistical analysis)	Thapa et al. (2023)					
Urban Forests	Stuttgart, Karlsruhe, & Heilderberg, Germany	Remote sensing and GIS (Participatory mapping)	Baumeister et al. (2022)					

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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